

Peroxidases. Part III. A Potentiometric Method of Estimating their Activity.

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The observation was made sometime ago (Dey and Sitharaman, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 9, 479) that hydroquinone was oxidised to quinhydrone by peroxidase in presence of hydrogen peroxide, and on the basis of this observation a method for estimating the peroxidase activities of plant saps was elaborated (*loc. cit.*). In that method a known weight of hydroquinone and a known amount of hydrogen peroxide were taken along with the necessary buffer, a fixed volume of peroxidase solution or sap added and the mixture stirred for a definite period, the reaction vessel being kept at 10-13° throughout the experiment. After the reaction was inhibited by the addition of hydrochloric acid, the liquid was quickly filtered through an Allihn tube, the precipitate of quinhydrone dissolved in a mixture of alcohol and hydrochloric acid (1:1), a solution of potassium iodide added and the liberated iodine titrated against standard thiosulphate using starch as an indicator. A correction for the quinhydrone lost had to be made by carrying out a blank with a known amount of quinhydrone and without the hydrogen peroxide under identical conditions. The correction applied was, therefore, empirical. No knowledge as to whether the hydrogen peroxide had reacted completely, or not was obtainable, nor was it possible to say if the amount of hydrogen peroxide that had disappeared corresponded with the amount of oxidation of the substrate.

The present investigation has been undertaken with the object of supplying this deficiency by applying potentiometric methods for the determination of (a) the substrate, (b) the hydrogen peroxide left over and (c) the quinhydrone formed. Thus the loss of quinhydrone during the operations of filtration and washing involved in the previous processes might be avoided.

The use of ceric sulphate in the determination separately of hydrogen peroxide and hydroquinone by Furman and Wallace (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 51, 1449; 1930, 52, 1443) had encouraged the hope at the beginning that the same reagent could be employed for estimating the two substances in the peroxidase reaction mixture. The problem did not appear, however, to be very simple, the chief

difficulty encountered being that of determining the end-point accurately. In fact no sharp end-point could be recognised on titrating mixtures of known amounts of hydrogen peroxide and hydroquinone against ceric sulphate, the potential changing continuously without showing any break even at the point corresponding to the stage of oxidation of both hydrogen peroxide and hydroquinone. Attempts made by using different electrode systems, to counteract the influence of polarisation caused chiefly by the quinone formed as a result of the oxidation of hydroquinone, did not lead to any improvement. It was found in the course of these experiments that the reaction between ceric sulphate and hydrogen peroxide was dependent on the hydrogen-ion concentration and in solutions, where the latter was reduced by sodium acetate, the reaction became practically nil, although under the same conditions, the hydroquinone was quantitatively oxidised (*vide* Table I). When these estimations were carried out with mixtures, however, no end-point was discernible either at the stage corresponding to the individual oxidation of hydroquinone or of the complete reaction of both.

Attention was next directed to the possibility of determining the hydroquinone alone in the reaction mixture after destruction of the hydrogen peroxide left over by means of catalase extracts. The latter were prepared from ox-kidney according to the method described by Morgulis and co-workers (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1926, 58, 521). Here, too, no satisfactory end-point could be reached and it was noticed in a blank experiment carried out with the sap alone that the plant sap itself consumed considerable quantities of the ceric sulphate, which was a powerful oxidising agent. No definite end-point could be obtained, however, even for the titration of the blank. The use of ceric sulphate as an oxidant had, therefore, to be ultimately abandoned on account of these difficulties. The failure is very probably caused by the fact that the oxidation potential of hydrogen peroxide is an uncertain factor, and in a mixture of hydrogen peroxide and hydroquinone the difference in oxidation potentials of the two substances might be so small that no selective oxidation was possible with the consequence that both were simultaneously oxidised.

Attempts were next made to destroy the excess of hydrogen peroxide by adding catalase and then estimating (i) the quinhydrone formed by thiosulphate in acetic acid medium (Rzyńkowski, *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1925, 31, 371) and (ii) the excess of hydroquinone left over by potassium dichromate in dilute sulphuric acid medium in

another aliquot part (Kolthoff, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1926, **48**, 745). These experiments have been entirely successful and have led to the development of a reliable potentiometric method for estimating the peroxidase activities of plant saps.

EXPERIMENTAL.

About 0.3 g. of pure hydroquinone (Kahlbaum) was weighed accurately into a dry, clean boiling tube and the test tube placed in powdered ice in a Dewar flask. 5 C.c. of buffer consisting of sodium acetate and hydrochloric acid of p_H 4.58, which is in the optimal p_H region for the reaction (*cf.* Dey and Sitharaman, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, **8**, 499) and 2 c.c. of 1% hydrogen peroxide were added and the liquid stirred vigorously with a mechanical stirrer while 5 c.c. of the sap were added. The time is noted when the addition is over, and precisely at the end of 15 minutes, 5 c.c. of 1.0*N* hydrochloric acid was added to inhibit the reaction. A minute later 5 c.c. of 1.0*N* sodium acetate solution were added to neutralise the hydrochloric acid and yet another minute later 1 c.c. of catalase extract. The reaction was allowed to proceed for 15 minutes at the end of which the liquid was made up to 100 c.c. with freshly boiled distilled water at the laboratory temperature.

A blank exactly as above but without the hydroquinone was carried out and the liquid made up to 100 c.c. in the same way.

20 C.c. of each were titrated against standard potassium dichromate using normal calomel electrode and a platinum electrode in a solution of about 1.5*N* sulphuric acid. The platinum electrode was ignited after every titration in a spirit lamp flame.

The enzyme-reacted solution (40 c.c. or 60 c.c. as the case may be) was titrated against standard sodium thiosulphate. The electrode system employed at first was gold and platinum (*cf.* experiments with horse radish sap), but was later changed with advantage to a system of gold and Veibel's quinhydrone electrode (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, **123**, 1103). The liquid was about 2*N* with respect to acetic acid and the titrant in this case was added drop by drop. The equilibrium potential was attained pretty quickly in the early stages of the titration but near the equivalence point it was found to take longer time to attain equilibrium.

The results of the experiments are given in Tables II, III and IV. Titrations with thiosulphate give the quinhydrone (quino part alone)

calculated as hydroquinone oxidised (1 mol. of quinone = 1 mol. of hydroquinone). Titrations with dichromate after correction for blank give the hydroquinone left over unoxidised. (In this is included the hydroquinone part of quinohydrone). The sum of these two quantities must be equal to the hydroquinone taken. As may be seen from the tables, the values obtained for the total hydroquinone from the titrations agree well with the weight actually taken for the experiments, the experimental error being less than 1 %.

TABLE I (a).

15 C.c. of hydroquinone soln., 25 c.c. of 4*N*-HCl and 60 c.c. of water titrated against ceric sulphate using platinum and normal calomel electrodes. Vol. at the equiv. point = 12.05 c.c.

Voltage	...	0.2520	0.4545	0.4699	0.7455	0.7717
Burette reading	...	17.17	29.20	29.25	29.30	29.35

TABLE I (b).

15 C.c. of hydroquinone solution, 25 c.c. of 1.0*N*-sodium acetate solution and 60 c.c. of water titrated against ceric sulphate using platinum and normal calomel electrodes. Vol. at equiv. point = 12.15 c.c.

Voltage	...	0.0260	0.1175	0.1335	0.1575	0.1850	0.2315
Burette reading	...	29.35	34.35	36.35	38.35	40.35	41.35
Voltage	...	0.2410	0.2575	0.3155	0.3520	0.3705	
Burette reading	...	41.40	41.45	41.50	41.55	41.60	

These results show that the potentiometric determination of hydroquinone using ceric sulphate as the oxidant proceeds equally well in hydrochloric and in acetic acid medium. In the case of hydrogen peroxide, the estimations could be carried out satisfactorily in hydrochloric acid medium, the potentials being found to conform to the observations of Furman and Wallace (*loc. cit.*). When, however, the titrations were done in sodium acetate medium, it became clear that the reaction was not proceeding at all since there was no decolourisation, and after some time the ceric sulphate was hydrolysed.

A series of blanks carried out without hydrogen peroxide with the three saps, conditions being the same, both at 0° and at 13° shows that

the influence of dehydrogenases, even if present, is practically nil, but the lower temperature was chosen chiefly on account of convenience. The following are the results obtained.

TABLE II.

Sap.	Results at 0°		Results at 13°	
	H.Q. taken.	H.Q. found.	H.Q. taken.	H.Q. found.
Horse radish	0.2976	0.2974	0.3030	0.3024
Chow-chow	0.2992	0.2986	0.2984	0.2978
Red radish	0.2982	0.2978	0.2976	0.2978

TABLE III(a).

Experiments with horse-radish (Raphanus sativus) (sap not dialysed).

EXPERIMENT I.

Wt. of hydroquinone taken = 0.3015 g. 40 C.c. of the enzyme-reacted solution against 0.04806N-Na₂S₂O₃. Au-Pt electrode system.

Voltage ...	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.0068	0.0070
Burette reading ...	15.55	16.55	17.55	18.55	19.05	20.05	20.55	20.65	20.70	20.75

(The voltage indicated was zero until very near the end-point, when there was a sudden and sharp rise in potential which hardly changed at all on further addition of the reagent. The approach near the end-point was easy to recognise from the tendency shown by the galvanometer to indicate a rise in voltage.)

TABLE III (b).

20 C.c. of the enzyme-reacted solution against 0.1039N-K₂Cr₂O₇. Pt—N-calomel electrodes.

Voltage.	Burette reading.	$\Delta E / \Delta C$ (m.volt/c.c.).
0.4363	27.05	164
0.4415	27.10	310
0.4600	27.15	610
0.4920	27.20	840 c.c.
0.5215	27.25	590
0.5495	27.30	560
0.5730	27.35	470

TABLE III(c).

20 C. c. of blank solution under the same conditions of acidity as above, viz., 2*N* with respect to H₂SO₄ against 0.1039*N*-K₂Cr₂O₇. Pt—*N*-calomel electrodes.

H. Q. taken	Voltage.	Burette reading.	$\Delta E / \Delta C$ (m.volt/c.c.)
= 0.3015 g.			
H. Q. corresp. to K ₂ Cr ₂ O ₇ titration = 0.2358 g.	0.3810	27.40	230
	0.3925	27.45	300
	0.4075	27.50	360
H. Q. corresp. to Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ titration = 0.0682 g.	0.4255	27.55 ... 0.15 c.c.	
	0.4390	27.60	270
Calc. value for total H. Q. = 0.3040 g.	0.4465	27.65	150
	0.4530	27.70	130

TABLE IV.

Experiments with horse-radish (R. sativus) (sap not dialysed).

	Expt. II.	Expt. III.
Hydroquinone taken	... 0.2976 g.	0.2988 g.
H. Q. unreacted (from K ₂ Cr ₂ O ₇ titration)	... 0.2325	0.2501
H. Q. reacted (from thiosulphate titration)	... 0.0635	0.0415
Total H. Q. (found from expt.)	... 0.2950	0.2986
Electrode system used	... Au/Pt	Au/Pt
	Pt— <i>N</i> -cal.	Pt— <i>N</i> -cal.
Limit of accuracy	... —0.87 %	—0.067 %

TABLE V(a).

Experiments with chow-chow (Sechium edule) (sap dialysed).

Wt. of H. Q. taken = 0.2950 g. 40 C. c. enzyme-reacted soln. against 0.04806 *N*-Na₂S₂O₃. Au-Veibel's quinhydrone electrodes.

Voltage.	Burette reading.	$\Delta E / \Delta C$ (m.volt/c. c.).
0.0679	36.00	
0.0729	36.05	
0.0805	36.10	210
0.0910	36.15	308
0.1064	36.20 ... 4.60 c. c.	
0.1185	36.25	242
0.1265	36.30	160

TABLE V(b).

20 C. c. enzyme-reacted solution against 0.1039 N-K₂Cr₂O₇. Pt-N-calomel electrodes.

Voltage.	Burette reading.	$\Delta E / \Delta C$ (m.volt/c.c.).
0.3585	28.50	
—	—	
0.4759	36.65	328
0.4923	36.60	974
0.5410	36.65 ... 8.15 c.c.	
0.5538	36.70	256

TABLE V(c).

20 C. c. blank solution against 0.1039 N-K₂Cr₂O₇. Pt-N-calomel electrodes.

H. Q. taken	= 0.2950 g.	Voltage.	Burette reading.	$\Delta E / \Delta C$ (m.volt/c.c.).
H. Q. corresp. to K ₂ Cr ₂ O ₇ titration	= 0.2315 g.	0.4865	28.30	110
H. Q. corresp. to Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ titration	= 0.0608 g.	0.4920	28.35 ... 0.05 c.c.	
Calc. value for total H. Q.	= 0.2923 g.	0.4958	28.40	76
		0.4976	28.54	36

TABLE (Vd).

Experiments with chow-chow, (Sechium edule) (sap dialysed).

In this series of experiments, combination of Veibel's quinhydrone and gold electrode gave better results in the estimation of quinhydrone by thiosulphate, the end-point being sharper. The hydroquinone was estimated using Pt/N-cal. combination.

	Expt. II.	Expt. III.
H. Q. taken	0.2959	0.2914
H. Q. (unreacted)	0.2386	0.2372
H. Q. reacted	0.0555	0.0536
Total H. Q. (found)	0.2941	0.2908
Electrode system	Au/Veibel Pt/N-cal.	Au/Veibel Pt/N-cal
Limits of accuracy	-0.6%	-0.2%

TABLE VI (a).

Experiments with red radish (Raphanus sativus) red variety.

In expt. I the undialysed sap was used; in expt. II and III the dialysed sap was used.

EXPERIMENT I.

Wt. of H. Q. taken = 0.2984 g. 40 C.c. of enzyme-reacted soln. against 0.04806N-Na₂S₂O₃. Au/Veibel's quinhydrone electrodes.

Voltage.	Burette reading.	$\Delta E / \Delta C$ (m.volt/c.c.).
0.0245	29.90	
—	—	
0.0965	34.70	
0.1075	34.75	220
0.1240	34.80 ... 4.90 c.c.	330
0.1355	34.85	230

TABLE VI (b).

20 C.c. enzyme-reacted soln. against 0.1039 N-K₂Cr₂O₇. Pt/N-cal. electrodes.

Voltage.	Burette reading.	$\Delta E / \Delta C$ (m.volts/c.c.).
0.3567	31.50	
...	...	
0.4490	39.45	386
0.4683	39.50	724
0.5045	39.55 ... 8.05 c.c.	340
0.5215	39.60	

TABLE VI (c).

20 C.c. blank solution against 0.1039 N-K₂Cr₂O₇. Pt/N-cal. electrodes.

Voltage.	Burette reading.	$\Delta E / \Delta C$ (m.volt/c.c.).
0.2550	31.30	
0.2805	31.35	510
0.3105	31.40 ... 0.10 c.c.	600
0.3350	31.45	490
0.3475	31.50	250

H. Q. taken	... 0.2984 g.
II. Q. corresp. to K ₂ Cr ₂ O ₇ titration	... 0.2272 g.
II. Q. corresp. to Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ titration	... 0.0616 g.
Calc. value for total II. Q.	... 0.2918 g.

(This is the only case where the error exceeds 1%, possibly because the sap was not dialysed. In experiments II and III where the sap had been dialysed before use, the error does not exceed 1%).

TABLE VI (d).

Experiments with red radish (Raphanus sativus).

In experiment I, the undialysed sap was used and in experiments II and III, the dialysed sap was used.

	Expt. II.	Expt. III.
H. Q. taken	0.2968	0.3006
H. Q. unreacted	0.2272	0.2344
" " reacted	0.0666	0.0633
Total H. Q. (found)	0.2938	0.2977
Electrode system	Au/Veibel Pt/N-cal.	Au/Veibel Pt/N-cal.
Limit of accuracy	-1%	-0.98%

The high error may be due to undialysed sap.

In the titration, where the quinhydrone was titrated against $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ using Veibel's quinhydrone electrode, a salt bridge was used for the electrode.